

DIAGNOSIS AND OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LARYNGITIS

Sabirova Shakhlo Bakhtiyorovna
Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
Bakiyev Shavkatbek Sherzodovich
Samarkand State Medical University

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Abstract: The disease usually begins acutely, against the background of general satisfactory condition and, as a rule, normal or subfebrile body temperature. At the beginning of the disease, patients complain of a feeling of dryness, persistence, and soreness in the throat. The voice becomes rough, gradually develops hoarseness, sometimes - up to aphonia. Changes in the voice are due to inflammatory edema of the mucous membrane of the vocal folds and larynx, increased formation of sputum. On the 2-3rd day of the disease may appear dry cough. It is accompanied by scanty discharge of viscous mucous sputum, the amount of which may further increase, and its character may change up to purulent sputum, especially in case of tracheitis.

Key words: acute laryngitis laryngitis, larynx, acute inflammation of the mucous membrane.

Introduction. Acute laryngitis, which develops as a result of hypothermia, overstrain of the voice or injury to the larynx, usually proceeds without worsening the general condition of the patient. The disease that occurs against the background of an infectious disease (ARVI, influenza, etc.) is accompanied by an increase in body temperature to febrile numbers and a violation of the general condition. Also, an increase in temperature to febrile figures indicates the addition of inflammation of the lower respiratory tract or the transition of catarrhal inflammation of the larynx to phlegmonous. Infiltrative and abscessing forms of acute laryngitis are characterized by severe sore throat, impaired swallowing (including fluid), severe intoxication, and increasing symptoms of laryngeal stenosis. The severity of clinical manifestations is directly correlated with the severity of inflammatory changes.

The duration of acute catarrhal laryngitis usually ranges from 5 to 10 days. Under unfavorable conditions, for example, violation of the vocal regime, inadequate therapy, etc., acute catarrhal laryngitis can turn into infiltrative or phlegmonous or into a chronic form.

Conclusions: Thus, it is necessary to differentiate acute catarrhal laryngitis, which arose on the background of hypothermia or ARVI, with acute catarrhal laryngitis in persons using voice for professional purposes, which developed against the background of overload of the vocal apparatus, since the treatment tactics will be different. The latter is always characterized by excessive vocal load preceding the onset of the disease and isolated changes in the larynx, manifested, as a rule, by marginal hyperemia of the free edge of the vocal folds and their hypotension, as well as hyperemia of the interdental space against the background of unchanged mucous membrane of other parts of the larynx.

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